

At maturity, 10 main panicles were randomly harvested to determine spikelet fertility for each cross (see table). BPI-76 showed normal fertility with indicas, the tongil, and one japonica. Fertility with N22 was highly variable among japonicas or indicas.

Fertility was normal in all crosses with Moroberekan.

Thus, the efficacy of the wide compatibility gene varies from variety to variety. Although the gene of Moroberekan was very effective, it may not be the best to use in breeding

programs because of its poor performance under lowland conditions. Acceptable varieties with efficient wide adaptability gene need to be isolated or developed. □

Breeding methods

Sensitivity of upland rice genotypes to gamma radiation

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We irradiated 3 genotypes of upland rice—Sathi 34-36, a local high-yielding, late, and tall genotype; IET2473, dwarf, mid-early, and coarse-grained; and Culture 102-5, semidwarf with medium duration and long, fine grain—with 5, 10, 15, and 20 kR doses of gamma rays. The experiment, with 2 replications, measured germination percentage, and root and shoot length at 10 d after planting.

Germination percentage was not appreciably reduced by gamma radiation. Root lengths were progressively reduced from 0 kR (7.14 cm) to 20 kR (3.82 cm) (see figure). Of the 3 genotypes, Culture 102-5 had longest roots at 0 kR and shortest at 20 kR. Gamma radiation did not reduce shoot lengths except in Culture 102-5.

Analysis of variance confirmed that radiation effects on root and shoot lengths varied significantly among varieties. The root length of Culture 102-5 was reduced 0.30 cm for every kR unit increase in radiation, compared to an average of 0.09 cm/kR unit for the 2 other varieties. Radiation reduced shoot

Effect of gamma ray doses on root and shoot lengths of 3 upland rice genotypes. Gujarat, India, 1987.

length of Culture 102-5, increased those of Sathi 34-36, but had no effect on those of IET2473.

We used rate of reduction in all three seedling characters per unit increase of

kR as the criteria for measuring sensitivity.

Culture 102-5 was clearly the most sensitive among the varieties tested. □

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